

Теорія та методика навчання

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Teaching Students the DMIP Methodology as a Modern Approach to Metaphor Translation

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Abstract. The paper explores the potential teaching benefits for the “Translation” specialty students about the DMIP (Deliberate Metaphor Identification Procedure) method, or the method of identifying deliberate metaphors, for detecting communicatively conditioned metaphors in a discursive context, as well as the possible benefits for involving this method at the stage of translation text analysis, and thus, as a result, establishing a better understanding of the metaphor and the text and its translation imagery. The topic of the research on approaches to metaphor translation is quite developed in modern science, but specifically the DMIP method and the benefits of using it in an educational context remain insufficiently researched in Ukrainian translation studies and pedagogy. The article offers a detailed overview about the existing scientific opinion on the the method effectiveness towards identifying deliberate metaphors in a linguistic context, the classification and definition of deliberate metaphor and its application in the translation and choice context in approaches to it. The theoretical basis of the study makes it possible to conduct a successful practical analysis towards all the process stages of identifying deliberate

metaphors in discourse. Considering from the pedagogical point of view the potential towards teaching the “Translation” specialty students, this methodology makes it possible to deepen the understanding of the text pragmatics and its communicative properties, which undoubtedly directly affects the choice of certain approaches to translation and adaptation of the metaphor. The analysis of the method of identifying deliberate metaphors and its application in the educational process demonstrates the certain method universality, its flexibility in different contexts, as well as the clarity in the algorithm of actions at the level of text translation analysis, which accordingly determines the consistency of the translation implementation. The described method and its steps detailed in the paper provide a roadmap for its introduction as a classroom activity. The topic has a clear potential for follow-up research.

Keywords: DMIP, translation studies, stylistics, metaphor, didactics.

Навчання студентів методики DMIP як сучасного підходу до перекладу метафори

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Анотація. У статті досліджуються потенційні переваги навчання студентів спеціальності «Переклад» методу DMIP (Deliberate Metaphor Identification Procedure), або методу виявлення навмисних метафор, для виявлення комунікативно обумовлених метафор у дискурсивному контексті, а також можливі переваги залучення цього методу на етапі перекладацького аналізу тексту, і, як наслідок, встановлення кращого розуміння метафори й образності

тексту та його перекладу. Тема дослідження підходів до перекладу метафор є досить розробленою в сучасній науці, але саме метод DMIP та переваги його використання в освітньому контексті залишаються недостатньо дослідженими в українському перекладознавстві та педагогіці. У статті пропонується детальний огляд існуючої наукової думки щодо ефективності методу виявлення навмисних метафор у лінгвістичному контексті, класифікації та визначення навмисної метафори і її застосування в контексті перекладу й вибору підходів до неї. Теоретична основа дослідження дозволяє провести практичний аналіз усіх етапів процесу виявлення навмисних метафор у дискурсі. З точки зору педагогічного потенціалу навчання студентів спеціальності «Переклад», ця методологія дає змогу поглибити розуміння прагматики тексту та його комунікативних властивостей, що безпосередньо впливає на вибір певних підходів до перекладу й адаптації метафори. Аналіз методу виявлення навмисних метафор і його застосування в навчальному процесі демонструє універсальність методу, його гнучкість у певних контекстах, а також чіткість алгоритму дій на рівні перекладацького аналізу тексту, що визначає послідовність реалізації перекладу. Описаний метод і його кроки, детально викладені в статті, надають план для його впровадження як навчальної діяльності. Тема має чіткий потенціал для подальших досліджень.

Ключові слова: DMIP, перекладознавство, стилістика, метафора, дидактика.

Problem statement. DMIP (Deliberate Metaphor Identification Procedure), or the method of identifying deliberate metaphors, is one of the modern approaches to identifying metaphors in discourse, the use of which in the context of teaching the translation students can have a number of advantages. The primary goal of involving this methodology is to simplify the text analysis process, in a logical way focused on the translator who deals with stylistically charged speech, either written or oral, the

role of metaphor in which can be the key to its meaning, and this, in turn, is of direct importance when adapting the text to the target language. The advantages of using DMIP are both analytical, and mainly determine how students understand the stylistic coloring of the text, and practical – what specific decisions will be made to adapt the metaphor or metaphorical means to the target language of translation.

Despite the central role of a metaphor in the meaning creation process and a stylistically charged text symbolism, the educational training of translators traditionally emphasizes the linguistic equivalence in this significant text element adaptation, however, the systematic comprehension and awareness about the versatility of a metaphor within the framework of its communicative role are often ignored in the training of future translators. Talking about the pragmatic nature of a metaphor, it should be emphasized that it directly determines the intentionality of its use, and therefore the focus on the pragmatics of metaphorical expression is extremely important for the “Translation” specialty students. The lack of systematic approaches to the identification of a metaphor and a deliberate metaphor in particular leads to the situation when translation students do not have a universal tool for interpreting a metaphor in discourse. As a result, the metaphoric character of the expression becomes a secondary element in translation, which in turn can lead to a distortion of the original text pragmatics. Incorrect or inaccurate translation, the use of partial equivalents or descriptive translation can lead to changes in the meaning, character and tone in the target text.

DMIP offers a structured approach that has been theoretically substantiated and repeatedly used as a proven approach to distinguishing metaphors in a text, as well as highlighting its communicative meaning. The pragmatic intention of the metaphorical expression appears central within the framework of this method. The use of this technique in the educational process has a high potential, which still remains insufficiently studied. The lack of empirical research with the integration of this method into the educational process determines the scientific interest in the topic. The

study of this problem is valuable for the further development of the methodology involved in the educational process. The training of future translators in modern conditions should aim to develop the cognitive and analytical skills of the “Translation” specialty students, since the ability to creatively analyze the text will always distinguish a human translator from any type of machine translation.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The theoretical framework for the paper relies on several fundamental works regarding metaphor, DMIP and pedagogical approaches to teaching translation. These include “DMIP: A method for identifying potentially deliberate metaphor in language use” by Burgers, C., Krennmayr, T., Reijnierse, W. G., & Steen, G. J. The paper introduces DMIP (Deliberate Metaphor Identification Procedure) as a revised and complete systematic method for identifying potentially deliberate metaphors in all natural language-based discourses, and as one that relies on the semiotic approach to text analysis [1]. The authors of the paper build up the Deliberate Metaphor Theory (DMT), which is a complex set of ideas that aim to distinguish between deliberate metaphors, the ones that are used intentionally to achieve a specific effect in communication, and non-deliberate metaphors – the ones that can be classified as routine or regular conventional expressions that became a norm in a language [1].

Among other researchers who have studied the use of DMIP in the context of translation and text analysis translation are Yajing Yu and Qiuyun Lu with their article “The Implication of DMIP on the Translation of Deliberate Metaphors in The Last Quarter of the Moon” [2]. In their article the authors argue that DMIP is not only a method for identifying potentially intentional metaphors, but also a process for fully analyzing a metaphor by tracing its cognitive connections with other elements of the text [2]. The DMIP methodology can be used to identify intentional metaphors in any text translation as one way of understanding the cognitive processes of processing the source and implementing adaptation in the target language, the same way as how the

conceptual network of metaphors in one language can potentially be superimposed on the worldview of another language [2].

The paper by Radetska, S., & Milova, O. examines the metaphor not just as a linguistic ornament but as a pragmatic tool that is capable of enhancing the pragmatic aim of an utterance as well as enriching the communication process and influencing an audience [3]. The paper focuses on cognitive approaches to metaphors and places it directly into the context of translation studies maintaining that metaphor's function is objectively universal across language and culture. The cognitive theory is an established framework, in which the metaphor is seen as a structural component that shapes an idea, both its expression and perception, taking into consideration the communicative intent behind it [3]. The pragmatics of the metaphor and how it influences human cognition are directly linked to the DMIP research process.

Other theoretical works defining the framework of the metaphor study include paper "Conceptual Metaphors in Poetry Interpretation: A Psycholinguistic Approach. Language and Cognition" by Rasse C., Onysko A. and Citron F., who look at conceptual metaphor in poetry's interpretation with the main focus on particular cognitive approaches [4]. Sydorenko's "Peculiarities of the Ukrainian translation of metaphors in the fantasy novel genre" provides an insight into various approaches to understanding and adapting metaphoric expressions in a genre specific discourse [5].

The pedagogical framework for the study is based on several works that includes "Current Assessment Practices in Ukrainian Translation Classroom" by Korol T., which provides an overview of widespread approaches to translation teaching and learning in the Ukrainian education system. It also serves as a basis for comparison [6]. The paper "Translation of Phraseological Units from English into Ukrainian: Didactic Aspects" by Filchuk T., Sukhanova T. and Lazaryeva O. studies modern approaches to idioms translation, which tend to include metaphoric expressions [7]. Sichkar, S., Kaminska, M., Bryk, M., Melko, K., Zhurkova, O., & Kharkevych, H. research the advertising slogans' translation and their communicative and pragmatic meanings

expressed with metaphoric means [8]. Yang, Zhihong & Li, Defeng in their paper “Translation Competence Revisited: Toward a Pedagogical Model of Translation Competence” look at translation competence and ways of achieving it [9].

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. DMIP use in translator training remains fairly unresearched, especially in the translation studies in Ukrainian higher education. While DMIP is not revolutionary at its core, this particular method has a potential in the educational context as it presents a model for analysis that aims to combat certain irregularities and unresolved issues that occur within the study of stylistics by translation students, many of which might have an idea of what a metaphor on a basic level as a notion is, but having no systematic approaches to it as both a stylistic and a direct communicative device may lead to a false understanding of the discourse pragmatics as a whole, and it creates a number of issues within the target text. Metaphor research and analysis in the context of translation quite often deal in abstraction and the DMIP introduction is one of the possible ways of putting in place a system which makes it easier and faster for a translation student to succeed.

The objectives of the paper. The main aim of the paper is to examine the educational and pedagogical value as well as the potential benefits of the Deliberate Metaphor Identification Procedure integration into the translator training at universities. The research focuses on the specific task of exploring whether the systematic order of the DMIP benefits the students’ performance and the translation quality. Other objectives include:

- to establish the relevance of DMIP in the context of translator training and the contemporary translation studies as a whole;
- to define the effectiveness of DMIP-based approach to the translation process in a classroom;
- to provide a framework for DMIP utilization in developing students’ translation competence.

Main body. The use of the DMIP methodology in the educational process gives students a systematic understanding in the meaning of metaphorical devices in the context of the source material. Considering DMIP as a methodology and its use within the framework of text translation analysis as a preparatory step before its direct adaptation, it should be mentioned that it helps the “Translation” specialty students distinguish between literal language, metaphorical and stylistically colored language. It also helps prevent unintentional transfer of metaphors and the statement ambiguity creation by contextualizing its stylistic properties in the original language, which thus effectively eliminates the possibility of erroneous changes in concepts and ideas in the adapted text; provides a tool for identifying ideological or evaluative concepts that were present in the discourse of the source text [1].

Analyzing the source text before starting translation requires a comprehensive understanding of the discourse and its meanings, and therefore the use of DMIP reduces the student translator’s dependence on subjective approaches to defining metaphor in discourse, and also determines the consistency of work both at the individual level (independent work of a student majoring in translation) and in the group (collective work of the group in the classroom).

DMIP is built upon MIP, but presents an extra linguistic core element to its system: it asks whether the identified metaphor is intentional or not? [1] And if it is, what is the exact intention, how it plays into the greater context, how it shapes the discourse and how the discourse shapes it in return. The deliberate nature of a metaphor changes the focus of the process.

The main argument for DIMP incorporation into translator training is based on the absence of a universal structured approach to metaphor decoding but is not limited to it. Overall, the divorce between the linguistic reality of a source text and a target text is something to consider as well. Conceptual Metaphor Theory is often viewed as one that operates in abstract terms and fails to provide an exact definition of what is to be

perceived as a metaphor, and moreover, it doesn't always consider the intent, only the result of the intent, which is the metaphor itself [1]. Cognitive processes behind metaphor production and its decoding are still abstract terms, but pragmatic function of an utterance is based on communicative logic and therefore holds in reality [2]. The pedagogical objectives of DMIP in translator training are clear: to teach students about cultural and ideological effects a deliberate metaphor can have; develop contextual approach strategies for translation based on the pragmatics of the text; assessment of the language acquisition level based on the quality of a metaphor-heavy translation produced by the "Translation" specialty students.

As it was previously mentioned, DMIP is an organized system that includes several steps aimed at defining the metaphoric expressions inside the text, the lexical network these expressions might establish in the text, the meanings created by this network, the pragmatic component that traditionally defines the communicative intention of the author/speaker. Defining the deliberate nature of a metaphor relies on the previously mentioned pragmatic aim and communicative intention [1]. All of these elements are key for successful text analysis and influence the process of translation, making the general procedure relatively easy to understand.

When introducing a text to the "Translation" specialty students, the very first task that has to be announced is to simply read the text without taking any notes. The format and size of the text is to be decided by the teacher depending on the following factors: students' fluency; the number of students in the classroom; the time limits within the class. It is important to match the difficulty level of the text with the level of fluency the students in the current classroom have as the general understanding of the topic in the studied discourse might not be sufficient, because students are required to be able to analyze the text based on a number of its details, which requires certain level of language fluency. The first step in the successful deliberate metaphor identification procedure training requires focus on the text – a competence students need to develop constantly. During this first step students need to define the

communicative situation, the goals of the studied text, and the intended audience as the general context. These details are essential and need to be discussed in the classroom. The teacher may ask students questions as soon as they finish reading. The questions should aim at defining the topic, the author and the audience. These questions need to be prepared in advance, but if the discussion leads the teacher to some new questions, they may ask these as well. In the process students may also be divided into groups to have a discussion on these matters with each other as it might encourage a creative approach to the matter.

The second step in the procedure is to identify metaphor-related words. Usually at this point in the analysis students are asked to write down every lexeme that has a metaphoric character. Lexical units are identified with the use of MIP that lies at the core of deliberate metaphor identification procedure, and which basically aims at determining the micro-context of each selected expression and establishing its basic meaning within the wider framework of the text [1]. The teacher can ask the students to present their lists of metaphor-related words providing reasons for choosing these particular lexical units. At this stage it is important to remember that not all the words the students decide to choose will be deliberate metaphors, and therefore not every word needs to be discussed in detail, so the teacher needs to control the presentations, their pace and focus. Selection of appropriate units from the text is essential at this particular step of the procedure as a training process both for saving time and having units of a higher quality to work with later.

The third step of the DMIP analysis in the classroom is designed to check the metaphorical signals behind the selected lexical units and/or phrases. The explicit and possible implicit cues that might signal metaphor use are tied to the literal meaning of a word or phrase and are based on the general deviation of the contextual meaning. The use of stylistic devices within such units is typical. At this stage the teacher has to explain what they are supposed to look for: comparison, analogy, extended metaphor framing, emphasis in the text – visual, lexical or contextual. The presence of these

elements does not necessarily defines a metaphor and states whether it is deliberate or not but simply establishes the metaphoric nature of the utterance. This step may be discussed in groups.

Step number four focuses on the source domain of the discussed lexical units. The source domain and its nature need to be analyzed on the basis of the text intention. Is the metaphor within an utterance compact or extended, and is the wider context built around it? What is the main argument for the metaphor use in this context? Does it provide an explanation for the matters the text focuses on? These questions are aimed at finding out the key indicators of a deliberate metaphor [1]. The answers to these questions may be discussed as well as written down.

The fifth step in the DMIP translation analysis looks at communicative intentions behind the text and its wider context. At this stage the students need to evaluate whether the discussed metaphoric expression is intended to: persuade the audience; explain certain phenomena; draw a parallel or compare the matter to something similar or completely different therefore highlighting the contrast; reframe the matter or the issue of the discourse presenting it from a different point of view; create vivid imagery on the level of conceptual system; evoke an emotional response and enforce its emotive impact. Explaining this step is important at the initial stage of the DMIP method introduction and integration, but the more students practice this method the less instruction is required. A discussion is essential to answer these and all of possible adjacent questions. This step aims to define whether the selected lexical units are deliberate metaphors based on the strategic communicative function they are designed to serve within the text.

At the last stage of the DMIP application the students are asked to classify each selected metaphor as deliberate or non-deliberate. The deliberate metaphor needs to be defined based on the previously established and discussed information. A deliberate metaphor is intended to make the audience perceive the expression according to the source domain and within the framework of the text; it brings the audience into the

world it creates. A non-deliberate metaphor is conventional in its nature and is processed without any metaphor awareness. Non-deliberate metaphors usually already have established equivalents in the source language and therefore are not the focus of the DMIP application in this case. It is also important to remember that any conventional metaphor can still be deliberate if the context of the text ties them into a wider conceptual metaphor network. These aspects need to be discussed with students in order to establish all the deliberate metaphors in the context. A presentation with analysis and justification for the claim is a standard way of evaluation at this stage.

The analysis provided by the “Translation” specialty students needs to be transparent and reliable. To achieve this students need to cite the linguistic evidence: the metaphor itself and any attached lexemes that may justify its metaphoric nature. The answer has to reference the context, the pragmatic aim and communicative intentions, the general discourse function. After completing the DMIP analysis the students need to provide a translation for the selected metaphors – first, out of context, then within the wider context, and then finally in the text as a whole. Approaches to metaphor translation depend on the choice the students make in the process and the character of the metaphor.

Conclusions. The paper set out to examine the pedagogical value and educational potential of the DMIP integration into the university-level translator training. The particular focus on the practical impact and clarity of the method in terms of the research allows to conclude that DMIP constitutes a methodologically sound tool which is designed to address the challenging areas of metaphor identification and translation based on their communicative nature and pragmatics in the source text.

The analysis confirms the DMIP relevance in the modern context of translation studies. It offers a systematic and transparent procedure with clearly defined steps that provide a clear roadmap for students to identify and translate deliberate metaphors into the target language. DMIP is cognitively oriented and therefore provides room for certain creative freedom and choice of translation approaches. The focus on the

communicative intention and discourse analysis is essential and valuable for training future translators.

The study demonstrates that the structure of the DMIP method provides clarity of the process and therefore positively impacts students' performance in the classroom. It supports an informed decision making by encouraging a careful analysis of the source text, raises the awareness of the specific metaphoric elements within the text, and as a result, provides opportunity for greater consistency in the translation.

The DMIP-based approach has a potential to be effective as a classroom activity. The topic remains relevant and open for further empirical research into its applicability to different text types translation.

List of References

1. Burgers C., Krennmayr T., Reijnierse W. G., Steen G. J. DMIP: A method for identifying potentially deliberate metaphor in language use. *Corpus Pragmatics*. 2018. Vol. 2. P. 129–147. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41701-017-0026-7>.
2. Yu Y., Lu Q. The implication of DMIP on the translation of deliberate metaphors in *The Last Quarter of the Moon*. *Forum for Linguistic Studies*. 2024. Vol. 6, No. 5. P. 94–104. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30564/fls.v6i5.6884>.
3. Radetska S., Milova O. Metaphor as a pragmatic tool for stylistic enhancement: Cognitive and translation studies perspectives. *Studia Philologica*. 2025. No. 1 (24). P. 244–253. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.28925/2311-2425.2025.2417>.
4. Rasse C., Onysko A., Citron F. Conceptual metaphors in poetry interpretation: A psycholinguistic approach. *Language and Cognition*. 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/langcog.2019.47>.
5. Sydorenko Y. I. Peculiarities of the Ukrainian translation of metaphors in the fantasy novel genre. *Науковий вісник Херсонського державного університету. Серія: Германістика та міжкультурна комунікація*. 2023. Вип. 1. С. 124–129.
6. Korol T. Current assessment practices in Ukrainian translation classroom: Teachers' survey results. *Advanced Education*. 2022. Vol. 9, No. 21. P. 135–160. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.266149>.

7. Filchuk T., Sukhanova T., Lazaryeva O. Translation of phraseological units from English into Ukrainian: Didactic aspects. *Вісник науки та освіти*. 2025. No. 3 (33). P. 33–49. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-6165-2025-3\(33\)-33-49](https://doi.org/10.52058/2786-6165-2025-3(33)-33-49).
8. Sichkar S., Kaminska M., Bryk M., Melko K., Zhurkova O., Kharkevych H. Training of future translators through advertising slogans translation. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*. 2023. Vol. 15, No. 2. P. 418–439. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/15.2/742>.
9. Yang Zh., Li D. Translation competence revisited: Toward a pedagogical model of translation competence. 2021. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-2070-6_6.
10. Wong S. Deliberate metaphor (use) in translation and interpreting: Is there such a thing? *Metaphor and the Social World*. 2025. Vol. 14, No. 2. P. 322–328. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1075/msw.24016.won>.
11. Jing Y., Jiang G. “No man is an island”: How Chinese netizens use deliberate metaphors to provide “depression sufferers” with social support. *Digital Health*. 2024. Vol. 10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076241228521>.
12. Reimann S., Scheffler T. Metaphors in online religious communication: Dataset and cross-genre metaphor detection. 2024.
13. Karasov V., Levchenko O. Metaphorization of the concept of joy in Oksana Zabuzhko’s fiction: A corpus-based approach. *Humanities Science Current Issues*. 2024. No. 1. P. 328–333. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24919/2308-4863/82-1-48>.
14. Tuna D., Kuleli M. Translation students’ conception of literary translation through metaphors. *İstanbul Üniversitesi Çeviribilim Dergisi (Istanbul University Journal of Translation Studies)*. 2023. P. 197–214. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26650/iujts.2023.1262786>.
15. Rutherford J., Merakchi K., He S. Collaborative learning for metaphor translation: Comparison of in-person and online settings. *Proceedings of the 5th Conference of the Association of Programmes in Translation and Interpreting Studies, UK and Ireland*. Belfast, 2023.
16. Conceptual metaphor theory in world language education: Theory, research, and pedagogy / ed. by I. Chavoshan, L. Fernández. London : Routledge, 2025.